

Sound Produced by an Impulsive Point Source

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Abstract

In this paper, sound produced by an impulsive point source is investigated. Firstly, definition of vortex sound, energy equation and equation of linear acoustic are expressed. Moreover Lighthill's Theory are introduced. Secondly, sound produced by impulsive point source is studied by using Lighthill's Theory.

1. Lighthill's Theory

1.1 Vortex Sound

Vortex sound is the sound produced as a by-product of unsteady fluid motions. It is part of the more general subject of aerodynamic sound.

We shall consider principally the production of sound by unsteady motions of a fluid. Any fluid that possesses intrinsic kinetic energy, that is, energy not directly attributable to a moving boundary, must possess vorticity. We shall see that in a certain sense and for a vast number of flows vorticity may be regarded as the ultimate source of the sound generated by the flow.

1.2 Energy equation

This equation must be used in its full generality in problems where energy is transferred by heat conduction, where frictional dissipation of sound is occurring, when shock waves are formed by highly nonlinear events, or when sound is being generated by combustion and other heat sources. For our purposes it will usually be sufficient to suppose the flow to be homentropic; namely the specific entropy s of the fluid is uniform and constant throughout the fluid, so that the energy equation becomes $s = \text{constant}$.

We may then assume that the pressure and density are related by an equation of the form

$$p = p(\rho, s), \quad s = \text{constant}. \quad (1)$$

This equation will be satisfied by both the mean (undisturbed) and unsteady components of the flow. Thus, for an ideal gas

$$p = \text{constant} \times \rho^\gamma, \quad \gamma = \text{ratio of specific heats}. \quad (2)$$

1.3 Lighthill's Theory

We consider a fluid in which a finite region only contains a non-steady fluctuating flow. Far from that region, we suppose the fluid to be uniform, with density ρ_0 and sound speed c_0 and to be at rest apart from the small motions included by the passage of sound waves generated by the unsteady flow.

Now, the exact equations expressing conservation of mass and momentum in a fluid are

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho v_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho v_i) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho v_i v_j + p_{ij}) = 0, \quad (4)$$

provided there are no extended sources of mass and no external forces acting on the fluid. p_{ij} is the compressive stress tensor. The vector $p_{ij}n_j$ is the force exerted across unit area with unit normal $\hat{n}$ by the fluid on the side to which $\hat{n}$ points on the fluid on the other side. If the fluid is inviscid, $p_{ij} = p\delta_{ij}$.

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For Newtonian fluid,

$$p_{ij} = p \delta_{ij} - 2\mu \left(e_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} e_{kk} \delta_{ij} \right) = p \delta_{ij} - \sigma_{ij} \quad (5)$$

where μ is the coefficient of viscosity, δ_{ij} the Kronecker delta and σ_{ij} is the viscous stress tensor defined by

$$\sigma_{ij} = 2\mu \left(e_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} e_{kk} \delta_{ij} \right), \text{ where } e_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial v_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (6)$$

is the rate of strain tensor.

Next multiply the continuity equation (3) by v_j :

$$v_j \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + v_j \frac{\partial \rho v_i}{\partial x_i} = 0.$$

Then (2) can be written as

$$\frac{\partial(\rho v_i)}{\partial t} = - \frac{\partial \pi_{ij}}{\partial x_i} \quad (7)$$

where $\pi_{ij} = \rho v_i v_j + (p - p_0) \delta_{ij} - \sigma_{ij}$ is called the momentum flux tensor and the constant pressure p_0 is inserted for convenience. In an ideal, linear acoustic medium, the momentum flux tensor contains only the pressure

$$\pi_{ij} \rightarrow \pi_{ij}^0 = (p - p_0) \delta_{ij} = c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0) \delta_{ij}$$

and the momentum equation then reduces to

$$\frac{\partial(\rho v_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0)) = 0. \quad (8)$$

If the continuity equation is written in the slightly modified form, then

$$\frac{\partial(\rho - \rho_0)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho v_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0. \quad (9)$$

Differentiating (8) with respect to 'x_i' gives

$$\frac{\partial^2(\rho v_i)}{\partial x_i \partial t} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} (c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0)) = 0.$$

Again, differentiating (9) with respect to 't' gives

$$\frac{\partial^2(\rho - \rho_0)}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial^2(\rho v_i)}{\partial x_i \partial t} = 0.$$

By eliminating the momentum density $\rho_0 v_i$, then we obtain the equation of linear acoustics satisfied by the perturbation density $\rho - \rho_0$

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) [c_0^2 (\rho - \rho_0)] = 0. \quad (10)$$

Because the turbulence is neglected in this approximation, and there are no externally applied forces or moving boundaries, the unique solution of this equation that satisfies the radiation condition of outgoing wave behavior is simply $\rho - \rho_0 = 0$.

It can now be asserted that the sound generated by the turbulence in the real fluid is exactly equivalent to that produced in the ideal, stationary acoustic medium forced by stress distribution

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_{ij} &= \pi_{ij} - \pi_{ij}^0 \\
 &= \rho v_i v_j + ((p - p_0) - c_0^2(\rho - \rho_0))\delta_{ij} - \sigma_{ij},
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

where T_{ij} is called the Lighthill stress tensor. That is **Lighthill’s acoustic analogy**. Indeed, we can rewrite (7) as the momentum equation for an ideal, stationary acoustic medium of mean density ρ_0 and sound speed c_0 subject to the externally applied stress T_{ij}

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial(\rho v_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}[c_0^2(\rho - \rho_0)] &= -\frac{\partial T_{ij}}{\partial x_j}, \\
 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\frac{\partial \rho v_i}{\partial t} \right) + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}[c_0^2(\rho - \rho_0)] &= -\frac{\partial^2 T_{ij}}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{12}$$

And modified continuity equation can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial(\rho - \rho_0)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho v_i}{\partial x_i} &= 0, \\
 \frac{\partial^2(\rho - \rho_0)}{\partial t^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial \rho v_i}{\partial x_i} \right) &= 0.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{13}$$

By eliminating the density $\rho_0 v_i$ between (12) and the continuity equation (13), we obtain **Lighthill’s equation**

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2(\rho - \rho_0)}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}[c_0^2(\rho - \rho_0)] &= \frac{\partial^2 T_{ij}}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}, \\
 \left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) [c_0^2(\rho - \rho_0)] &= \frac{\partial^2 T_{ij}}{\partial x_i \partial x_j}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{14}$$

This is the exact non-linear counterpart of (10). The problem of calculating the turbulence generated sound is therefore equivalent to solving this equation for the radiation into a stationary, ideal fluid produced by a distribution of quadrupole sources whose strength per unit volume is the Lighthill stress tensor T_{ij} .

2 Pulsating sphere and Sound produced by an impulsive point source

2.1 Pulsating sphere

Consider the motion produced by small amplitude radial pulsations of a sphere of mean radius a . Let the centre of the sphere be at the origin, and let its normal velocity be $v_n(t)$. There are no sources within the fluid, so that $q = 0$. Therefore,

$$\left. \begin{aligned}
 \nabla^2 \phi &= 0, & r > a, \\
 \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} &= v_n(t), & r = a
 \end{aligned} \right\} \text{where } r = |\underline{x}|.$$

The motion is obviously radially symmetric, so that

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \phi = 0, \quad r > a.$$

Hence,

$$\phi = \frac{A}{r} + B,$$

where $A = A(t)$ and $B = B(t)$ are functions of t , $B(t)$ can be discarded because the pressure fluctuations $\left(\sim -\rho_0 \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} \right)$ must vanish as $r \rightarrow \infty$. Applying the condition $\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial r} = v_n(t)$ at $r = a$, we then find

$$\phi = -\frac{a^2 v_n(t)}{r}, \quad r > a. \tag{15}$$

Thus, the pressure

$$p = -\rho_0 \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} = \rho_0 \frac{a^2}{r} \frac{dv_n(t)}{dt}$$

decays as $\frac{1}{r}$ with distance from the sphere, and exhibits the unphysical characteristic of

changing instantaneously everywhere when $\frac{dv_n}{dt}$ changes its value. For any time t , the volume flux $q(t)$ of fluid is the same across any closed surface enclosing the sphere. Evaluating it for any sphere S of radius $r > a$, as shown in Figure-1, we find

$$q(t) = \int_S \nabla \phi \cdot d\mathbf{S} = 4\pi a^2 v_n(t),$$

and we may also write

$$\phi = \frac{-q(t)}{4\pi r}, \quad r > a. \tag{16}$$

Figure. 1

2.2 Point source

The incompressible motion generated by a volume point source of strength $q(t)$ at the origin is the solution of

$$\nabla^2 \phi = q(t)\delta(\underline{x}), \text{ where } \delta(\underline{x}) = \delta(x_1)\delta(x_2)\delta(x_3). \tag{17}$$

The solution must be radially symmetric and given by

$$\phi = \frac{A}{r} \text{ for } r > 0. \tag{18}$$

To find A , we integrate (17) over the interior of a sphere of radius $r = R > 0$, and use the divergence theorem $\int_{r < R} \nabla^2 \phi d^3 \underline{x} = \int_S \nabla \phi \cdot d\mathbf{S}$, where S is the surface of the sphere. Then

$$\int_S \nabla \phi \cdot d\mathbf{S} = \left(\frac{-A}{R^2} \right) \times (4\pi R^2) = q(t).$$

Hence, $A = -\frac{q(t)}{4\pi}$ and $\phi = -\frac{q(t)}{4\pi r}$, which agrees with the solution (16) for the sphere

with the same volume outflow in the region $r > a$, radius of the sphere. This indicates that when we are interested in modelling the effect of a pulsating sphere at large distances $r \gg a$, it is permissible to replace the sphere by a point source (a monopole) of the same strength $q(t)$, rate of change of the volume of the sphere. This conclusion is valid for any pulsating body, not just a sphere.

The solution (18) for the point source is strictly valid only for $r > 0$, where it satisfies $\nabla^2 \phi = 0$. We write the solution in the form

$$\phi = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{-q(t)}{4\pi(r^2 + \epsilon^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \epsilon > 0, \text{ in which case } \nabla^2 \phi = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{3\epsilon^2 q(t)}{4\pi(r^2 + \epsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}}.$$

The last limit is just equal to $q(t)\delta(\underline{x})$. Indeed when ε is small $\frac{3\varepsilon^2}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}}$ is also small except close to $r = 0$, where it attains a large maximum $\sim \frac{3}{4\pi\varepsilon^3}$. Therefore, for any smoothly varying test function $f(\underline{x})$ and any volume V enclosing the origin

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_V \frac{3\varepsilon^2 f(\underline{x}) d^3 \underline{x}}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = f(0) \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_V \frac{3\varepsilon^2 d^3 \underline{x}}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}}.$$

Since

$$\int_V \frac{3\varepsilon^2 d^3 \underline{x}}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{3\varepsilon^2 r^2 \sin \theta dr d\theta d\phi}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{3\varepsilon^2 r^2 dr}{(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}},$$

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_V \frac{3\varepsilon^2 f(\underline{x}) d^3 \underline{x}}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = f(0) \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{3\varepsilon^2 r^2 dr}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}}.$$

And also we have, putting $r = \varepsilon \tan \alpha$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{3\varepsilon^2 r^2 dr}{(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} \frac{3\varepsilon^5 \tan^2 \alpha \sec^2 \alpha}{(\varepsilon^2 \sec^2 \alpha)^{\frac{5}{2}}} d\alpha = 3 \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} (1 - \cos^2 \alpha) \cos \alpha d\alpha = 1.$$

Thus,

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_V \frac{3\varepsilon^2 f(\underline{x}) d^3 \underline{x}}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = f(0) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{3\varepsilon^2 r^2 dr}{(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = f(0),$$

where the value of the last integral is independent of ε . This is the defining property of the three-dimensional δ function.

Thus, the correct interpretation of the solution

$$\phi = \frac{-1}{4\pi r} \text{ of } \nabla^2 \phi = \delta(\underline{x}) \tag{19}$$

for a unit point source ($q = 1$) is

$$\frac{-1}{4\pi r} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{-1}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad r \geq 0, \tag{20}$$

where $\nabla^2 \left(\frac{-1}{4\pi r} \right) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \nabla^2 \left(\frac{-1}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{3\varepsilon^2}{4\pi(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} = \delta(\underline{x}).$ (21)

2.3 Sound produced by an impulsive point source

The impulsive point source of strength $\delta(\underline{x})\delta(t)$ is non-zero for an infinitesimal time at $t = 0$ and generalizes the time-independent volume source. The usual convention, however, is to reverse the sign of the source and to consider the corresponding inhomogeneous wave equation in the form

$$\left(\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \right) \phi = \delta(\underline{x})\delta(t). \tag{22}$$

The source exists only for an infinitesimal instant of time at $t = 0$; therefore at earlier times $\phi(\underline{x}, t) = 0$ everywhere.

It is evident that the solution is radially symmetric, and that for $r = |\underline{x}| > 0$ we have to solve

$$\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \phi = 0, \quad r > 0. \quad (23)$$

The identity

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \phi = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} (r\phi) \quad (24)$$

permits us to write (23) in the form of the one-dimensional wave equation for $r\phi$:

$$\frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} (r\phi) - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} (r\phi) = 0, \quad r > 0. \quad (25)$$

This has the general solution $r\phi = \Phi(t - \frac{r}{c_0}) + \psi(t + \frac{r}{c_0})$, where Φ and ψ are arbitrary functions. Hence, the general solution of (3.29) is

$$\phi = \frac{\Phi\left(t - \frac{r}{c_0}\right)}{r} + \frac{\psi\left(t + \frac{r}{c_0}\right)}{r}, \quad r > 0. \quad (26)$$

The first term on the right represents a spherically symmetric disturbance that propagates in the direction of increasing values of r at the speed of sound c_0 as t increases, whereas the second represents an incoming wave converging toward $\underline{x} = \underline{0}$. We must therefore set $\psi = 0$, since it represents sound waves generated at $r = \infty$ that approach the source rather than sound waves generated by the source and radiating away from the source. This is a causality or radiation condition, that (in the absence of boundaries) sound produced by a source must radiate away from the source. An event in which sound waves converge on a point from all directions at infinity is so unlikely as to be impossible in practice; it would be the acoustic analogue of the far-scattered pieces of a broken cup spontaneously reassembling.

To complete the solution it remains to determine the function Φ . We do this by extending the solution down to the source at $r = 0$ by writing

$$\phi = \frac{\Phi\left(t - \frac{r}{c_0}\right)}{r} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Phi\left(t - \frac{r}{c_0}\right)}{(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}, \quad r \geq 0. \quad (27)$$

Let us substitute this into (18) and examine what happens as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. By direct calculation we find

$$\nabla^2 \phi = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} (r\phi) = -\frac{3\varepsilon^2 \Phi(t - \frac{r}{c_0})}{(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} - \frac{-2\varepsilon^2 \Phi'(t - \frac{r}{c_0})}{c_0 r (r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \frac{\Phi''(t - \frac{r}{c_0})}{c_0^2 (r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}},$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial t^2} - \nabla^2 \phi &= \frac{3\varepsilon^2 \Phi(t - \frac{r}{c_0})}{(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} + \frac{2\varepsilon^2 \Phi'(t - \frac{r}{c_0})}{c_0 r (r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &\rightarrow 4\pi \Phi(t) \delta(\underline{x}) + 0 \text{ as } \varepsilon \rightarrow 0, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where the δ function in the last line follows from (21), and the '+0' is obtained by noting that for any smoothly varying test function $f(\underline{x})$ and any volume V enclosing the origin

$$\begin{aligned} \int_V \frac{2\varepsilon^2 f(\underline{x}) d^3 \underline{x}}{r(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} &\approx f(0) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{2\varepsilon^2 d^3 \underline{x}}{r(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = f(0) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{8\pi\varepsilon^2 r dr}{(r^2 + \varepsilon^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &= 8\pi\varepsilon f(0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \varepsilon \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Hence, comparing (28) with the inhomogeneous wave equation (22) we find

$$\Phi(t) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \delta(t),$$

and the solution (27) becomes

$$\phi(\underline{x}, t) = \frac{1}{4\pi r} \delta\left(t - \frac{r}{c_0}\right) = \frac{1}{4\pi|\underline{x}|} \delta\left(t - \frac{|\underline{x}|}{c_0}\right). \quad (30)$$

This represents a spherical pulse that is non-zero only on the surface of the sphere $r = c_0 t > 0$, whose radius increases at the speed of sound c_0 ; it vanishes everywhere for $t < 0$, before the impulsive source is triggered.

Conclusion

Vortex Sound is the sound produced as a by-product of unsteady fluid motions. Sound produced by a source must radiate away from the source.

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